

THESIS - EM LYON BUSINESS SCHOOL
MS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, MARKETING & STRATEGY

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT:
IMPROVING EFFICIENCY OR PROFESSIONAL OBSOLESCENCE?**

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DATE: 2024

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1 ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence promises to increase the performance of projects and the efficiency of professionals, but raises the question of the obsolescence of traditional skills and roles. This research seeks to determine whether AI is a strategic necessity for the company or a threat to project managers, by analysing how it redistributes responsibilities within teams.

The research is based on a review of the state of the art and semi-structured interviews with project management experts from a variety of sectors, providing a rich and nuanced analysis of the integration of AI into project management. The results show a consensus on the performance gains achieved by automating repetitive tasks, optimising planning and communication, and enabling high-quality forecasts and predictions. However, human supervision is still essential to ensure that the solution is in line with the company's strategy, relevant to the context surrounding the project and its evolution, and meets the needs of the stakeholders. The study reveals that AI is transforming traditional roles and there is a need to adapt skills, processes, and application of project management methods. Project management professionals need to refocus on strategic tasks with high added value such as managing human relationships, making complex decisions, and delivering value and benefit to the company and clients.

This evolution of project management from the technical to the strategic requires a continuous re-qualification and training of skills to maintain the relevance of Project Managers.

This research is aimed at project management professionals as well as strategic managers and functions. It reveals how organisations can take advantage of AI in project management to remain competitive while avoiding the pitfalls of professional obsolescence. Strong organisational and cultural support is crucial to promote the acceptance of AI and to establish internal policies adapted to the challenges. This study adds to our understanding and anticipation of major transformations in project management in the age of AI

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3 PRESENTATION OF THE COMPANY'S ACTIVITY AND MAIN MISSIONS

3.1 A brief history

BioMérieux's expertise in biology is rooted in the unique history of the Mérieux family. In 1897, Marcel Mérieux, a pupil of Louis Pasteur, founded a medical analysis laboratory which became Institut Mérieux. His son, Dr Charles Mérieux, later introduced *in vitro* culture to revolutionise the manufacture of vaccines and diagnostic tests. In 1963, Alain Mérieux, Marcel's grandson, founded BioMérieux, a company dedicated to *in vitro* diagnostics. BioMérieux, a family business, has become a world leader in this field over the years.

Today, the company focuses on its two main missions:

- Improving patient care and consumer health protection through diagnostic solutions.
- Taking effective action against infectious diseases to help improve public health worldwide.

BioMérieux works mainly with healthcare professionals, medical laboratories, pharmaceutical companies and researchers. They use the company's products, solutions and services for medical diagnostics, infection monitoring and biomedical research.

Mention should also be made that BioMérieux is part of Institut Mérieux, the family holding company founded in Lyon in 1897 by Marcel Mérieux. Its aim is to devise and develop new approaches in the fields of diagnostics, immunotherapy, food safety and nutrition.

The group owns five companies that have made major advances in medicine and public health: BioMérieux, Mérieux NutriSciences, Transgene, ABL Inc. and Mérieux Equity Partners.

3.2 Background to the thesis: the Project Leader's role at BioMérieux

As a Project Leader at BioMérieux in the PMO department, I had to lead a one-year project to diagnose the artificial intelligence needs of project management professionals. This task was a preliminary study (pre-project) in the form of technical specifications with the aim of obtaining validation and funding to launch a project to integrate artificial intelligence into the group's project management toolkit.

To perform this diagnosis, we had to put together a team of around ten individuals, each with a defined role to play, such as producing the communication plan.

We put together an international team of internal key users with a variety of profiles to cover the full range of internal professions in project management roles: Project Managers, Project Leaders, PMOs, Program Managers and Portfolio Managers. Six workshops were held with these stakeholders to identify their issues, sort and assess their needs in terms of artificial intelligence capabilities in order of priority, and draft real-life practical applications.

A review of the state of the art was also carried out to identify existing use cases and artificial intelligence capabilities on the market.

4 INTRODUCTION

4.1 Presentation and justification of the research topic

The aim of this thesis is to contribute to the advancement of knowledge about AI in project management and to contribute to a better understanding of the synergy between AI and project management by exploring the efficiencies gained over traditional processes.

The problem is to “analyse the role of artificial intelligence in project management: will it make projects more efficient?”. The question is do we think AI is a strategic necessity or an option for improving project efficiency? To what extent is it an evolution or a revolution in efficiency and work standards?

It is essential to understand the impact of AI if we are to remain competitive in a period of transformation where AI seems to be a strategic turning point in project management beyond technological evolution.

The challenge is to analyse the state of the art of AI in project management and the potential impact in terms of productivity gains, quality of decision making and optimisation of resource allocation.

4.2 Hypothesis and research question

The effectiveness of AI in project management has not been proven. This thesis is based on the premise that the integration of AI is a strategic necessity, bringing unprecedented efficiency and redefining certain project management standards. However, this increased efficiency is only possible if we consider AI as a strategic tool for which we must take responsibility, with which we must learn to evolve and if we know how to use it.

For the research phase, this will potentially lead us to the question: does the implementation of AI-based solutions in project management lead to changes in project management evaluation metrics? How do we measure things before and after AI?

4.3 Main objective and contribution to academic debate

This thesis aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge about AI in project management and to contribute to a better understanding of the potential and the effectiveness of AI.

The challenge is to analyse the state of the art of AI in project management and the potential impact in terms of productivity gains, quality of decision making and optimisation of resource allocation.

The scope of existing publications covers:

- Artificial intelligence typologies applicable to project management.
- The impact of AI on project management disciplines.
The disciplines are: project integration management, project scope management, project cost management, project quality management, project resource management, project communication management, project risk management, project procurement management, project stakeholder management.
- What project managers expect from AI.

This thesis approaches the issue of improved efficiency and the risk of professional obsolescence in the project management profession.

5 STATE OF THE ART: AI IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

5.1 Background to project management

5.1.1 Introduction to project management

Projects have been around for as long as anyone can remember, and it's hard to trace their origins. In the Middle Ages, cathedral builders were already carrying out major infrastructure projects that required coordination between sponsors and contractors and technical innovations, such as arch thrusts. Over the years, projects evolved from improvised design to design that was separate from execution. Architects coordinated construction using large-scale drawings and technical plans. Project management did not exist as a discipline or profession, but was confused with existing professions. The architects of the cathedrals enjoyed a high social status that was distinct from that of the builders. It was within the lodges that the master craftsmen passed on professional and technical values to the apprentices on the construction sites. There were many different types of engineering project, including industrial, military, roadworks and naval projects. The standardisation of project management emerged in the 1950s and 1960s influenced by major North American engineering projects such as aeronautics (space race) and Cold War military programmes (Garel, 2013).

Project management is a discipline that can be defined differently depending on individual perspectives, reference standards and methodologies. Projects vary in form and scope. Projects can be in multiple fields of activity such as computer projects, scientific research to launch a new drug or the organisation of a sports event (PRINCE2).

Project management is commonly presented as a set of planned, coordinated and controlled activities with the aim of achieving a defined objective by respecting defined constraints such as budget, time or quality.

Table 1: Comparison of project management definitions according to standards

References	Definition
APM Body of Knowledge	"Projects are transitional undertakings that lead to change and the achievement of planned objectives. Together, they combine to deliver the beneficial changes needed to implement, enable and satisfy the organisation's strategic intent" (APM Body of Knowledge)
ISO 21500	"Temporary effort to achieve one or more defined goals. Projects are carried out by temporary teams and provide deliverables, output elements, results and benefits" (ISO 21500)
PMBOK	"A temporary effort to create a unique product, service or result. The temporary nature of the projects implies a beginning and end to the work of the project or to a phase of the work of the project" (PMBOK)
PRINCE2	"Temporary organisation created for the purpose of providing one or more commercial products in accordance with an agreed business case" (PRINCE2)

These definitions are similar in that they emphasise the temporary nature of projects and their objective of producing concrete results. More specifically, ISO 21500 and PMBOK are focused on achieving a result, product or service, while PRINCE2 emphasises the delivery of commercial products and the APM Body of Knowledge focuses on achieving the organisation's strategic objectives.

Building a house involves carrying out specialised tasks such as laying foundations, building walls, installing windows as well as plumbing. These activities are outside the scope of project management, but project management is needed to coordinate and control these activities to ensure the consistency and efficiency of the overall process (PRINCE2).

5.1.2 Project life cycle

5.1.2.1 Introduction to the life cycle of a project

According to the Project Management Institute, the life cycle of a project is “the series of phases through which a project goes from its beginning to its completion [...] The effective execution of this performance area results in the following desired results:

- Development approaches consistent with project deliverables;
- A project life cycle consisting of phases that connect the delivery of business value and value to stakeholders from the beginning to the end of the project;
- A project life cycle consisting of phases that facilitate the delivery rate and development approach needed to produce project deliverables” (Project Management Institute, 2017).

Projects are typically organised into phases determined by governance and control needs. These phases must follow a logical sequence, with a beginning and an end, and must use resources to provide deliverables. In order to manage the project effectively throughout its life cycle, a set of activities must be carried out during each phase. The project phases are collectively known as the project life cycle. The project life cycle extends from the beginning of the project to its end. Phases are divided by decision points, which may vary depending on the organisational environment. The decision points facilitate the governance of the project. At the end of the last phase, the project must have provided all deliverables. To manage a project throughout its life cycle, project management processes must be used for the project as a whole or for individual phases for each team or sub-project.

Figure 1: Life cycle of a project in traditional methodologies

Source: <https://businessmap.io/project-management/process>

The life cycle of a project is a roadmap for project execution that defines the flow and sequencing of activities in order to facilitate the management of the project from its design to its completion. This model includes the stages of the project, the operations in each phase, the deliverables involved and the control points (ISO 21500). Depending on the size, scope or methodology of the project, these stages may be designated differently but are grouped into five elements: project initiation, planning, execution, monitoring and controlling, and closure.

Figure2: The typical sequence of the five stages of a project

Source: <https://www.workamajig.com/blog/project-life-cycle>

The stages of a project's life cycle (initiation, planning, execution, monitoring and controlling, and closure) are not equal and vary according to the context of the project, its size, its scope and its project management methodology. The stages are not strictly compartmentalised and may share activities, objectives and resources.

5.1.2.2 The life cycles of innovation and agile methods

In agile methods such as Scrum or in innovative approaches such as Lean startup and Design Thinking, project life cycles are highly adaptable to changes and uncertainties.

A key principle of Agile methods is to ensure client satisfaction by delivering a product they consider to have added value as quickly as possible by offering a small set of features as soon as possible and developing them through iterations. Agile methods are based on client feedback and changes to the context and the project, rather than on a rigid roadmap (Gurusamy et al., 2016). In Scrum methodology, frequent adjustments are based on stakeholder feedback during the project life cycle divided into short and iterative sprints.

Continuous and rapid experimentation, as well as an approach focused on the user's problems and needs, form the basis of innovative approaches such as Design Thinking and Lean Startup. Design Thinking combines the divergent exploration of context, problems and solutions with a convergence process for choosing the solution (Gurusamy et al., 2016).

There are different life cycle forms, from the model managing planned and linear changes to the model dealing with iteratively emerging changes. The distinction between traditional and agile project management is no longer relevant. It is better to be concerned with the decisions of managers, who are increasingly opting for hybrid approaches, combining linear and iterative life cycles (APM Body of Knowledge). For example, if we incorporate the principles of Design Thinking (exploration and convergence) into each agile phase, this creates a space for prior analysis with diverse skills (Gurusamy et al., 2016). These combined methodologies provide a hybrid project management framework that facilitates innovation, adaptation and efficiency in an uncertain context.

Figure 3: Demonstration of a combination of methodologies in a hybrid project

Source: <https://www.gartner.com/en>

The illustration represents a life cycle combining Design Thinking to stimulate empathy and ideation, Lean Startup for experimentation and rapid validation, and agile for iterative development and continuous improvement.

5.1.3 Project effectiveness

5.1.3.1 Measuring effectiveness according to the iron triangle (cost, quality, timelines)

The notion of project success has evolved from a focus on implementation to taking full account of the project life cycle. This evolution is divided into four periods: from 1960-1980 the focus was on meeting deadlines, costs and specifications; from 1980-1990 there was the inclusion of key success factors and striving for stakeholder satisfaction; from 1990-2000 the key success factors became more strategic; and in the 21st century there is an alignment of projects with business strategy as a priority (Agarwal & Rathod, 2006).

Despite these developments, since the 1970s the main criteria anchored in project management have been cost, time and quality, which are represented by the “iron triangle” (Atkinson, 1999). This is the traditional standard for evaluating the success of projects. According to an exploratory study, project management professionals indicate that cost, time, functionality and quality remain their important criteria for assessing whether projects are performing well. Cost is considered the least vital criterion of the three for measuring success (Agarwal & Rathod, 2006).

This tool, also known as the triple constraint, interconnects the three constraints of a project, which are respectively impacted by developments in each of the three segments. To successfully manage a project, the constraints of the iron triangle must remain balanced so that if one aspect increases, the others must decrease. Cost and timelines are assumptions made at the start of the project while quality is influenced by the attitudes of project stakeholders that may evolve over the life cycle (Atkinson, 1999).

Figure 4: The triple constraints of projects

Source: <https://www.pmi.org/learning/thought-leadership/measuring-what-matters>

A key principle of project management is maintaining a balance between objectives and challenges while respecting the constraints of the time, cost and quality triptych. The iron triangle is as relevant today as it was in its early days, but project management has evolved to offer more choice in the way initiatives are managed (APM Body of Knowledge).

The life cycles of agile and innovative methods are different from traditional project management methodologies, so the criteria for project effectiveness are also different. The three main constraints in Design Thinking are desirability, feasibility and viability (Gurusamy et al., 2016).

Figure 5: Comparison of constraints in traditional and agile methodologies

Source: <https://www.projectmanagement.com/blog-post/5325/the-agile-triangle#>

In agile project management, value and quality are key success criteria as are the initial cost-quality-time criteria which are combined in a single set of constraints. This evolution in the assessment of effectiveness stems from a mismatch between the traditional assessment framework for managers and the need for project managers to be agile and adaptable, as well as a focus on maximising stakeholder-perceived value and quality (Kim, 2012).

The two basic concepts in assessing the effectiveness of a project are the success of the project management measured by the iron triangle as well as the success of the project evaluated in terms of meeting expectations, which evolve throughout the life cycle of the project (Agarwal & Rathod, 2006).

5.1.3.2 Questioning the main effectiveness criteria

Regarding project success, a study reveals that 47% of respondents believe that their organisation has demonstrated its ability to succeed in projects, 43% to meet the project budget and 40% indicated that their organisation benefited from projects carried out (Wellington, 2020). According to this study, the main reasons for these challenges are the growing number of projects to be managed, combined with poorly trained project managers and poor resource management. Projects that merely meet the “iron triangle” metrics are often considered to have little return on investment for organisations (Project Management Institute & PWC, 2022).

The iron triangle often serves as a basis for monitoring progress but does not provide enough information on the overall impact of the project nor does it guarantee results. It is essential to add other criteria such as environmental impact, return on investment or the intermediate results expected throughout the project. The iron triangle is made up of stable measurements but the results measurements must be scalable and controlled through performance monitoring (Project Management Institute & PWC, 2022). Focusing on immediate success factors, especially in terms of meeting budget and deadlines, is a narrow analysis that can lead to negative developments later on, resulting in project failure. Short-term success based on project implementation may mask harmful implications for further longer-term operations (Larsen & Myers, 1999).

Project management may have as its essence of value its evolutionary and dynamic nature (Atkinson, 1999) so it would be negligent to ignore changes in the levels of importance of success factors during the project implementation process (Larsen & Myers, 1999).

Projects may continue to fail because the cost-quality-time triptych does not promote success but rather seeks alignment with the project's initial estimates (Atkinson, 1999). Focusing on costs and deadlines to proclaim the success of a project presupposes the effectiveness of estimation models, and masks the crucial question of the functional realisation of the project as a criterion of success (Agarwal & Rathod, 2006). The organisation that initiates the project determines the scope, while the time and cost estimates are mere assumptions.

The iron triangle remains the key success factor for a project, although additional metrics have been proposed, such as the technical performance of the final system, and the benefits for the organisation and its stakeholders. However, a successful project also involves use by clients, project staff, appreciation by sponsors and improved organisational effectiveness (Atkinson, 1999). The notion of “success” of a project is complex, subjective and evolves over time. It depends on the moment of evaluation in the project cycle and the opinion of the stakeholder interviewed, which can also change over time, calling into question the ease with which projects can be judged as successful or unsuccessful (Larsen & Myers, 1999).

According to PRINCE2, which has three effectiveness criteria in addition to the iron triangle, project management has six main areas to manage: cost, timelines, quality, scope, benefit and risk. The scope variable defines and shares what the project is going to deliver, the benefit variable ensures that the results of the project match the expected benefits and the risk variable enables risks to be identified and managed. The traditional evaluation approach based on time, cost and quality is still relevant, but is not representative of the complete situation. KPIs are effective for summarising the progress of a project if they are consistent with the project variables: time, cost, quality, scope, benefits and risks (PRINCE2).

Measuring the operational effectiveness of a project is difficult to quantify and requires human relationships with stakeholders to ensure strategic alignment and perceived value (Project Management Institute & PWC, 2022). A project can be considered as successful if it respects the initial time and cost criteria even though it does not provide any value for the client or the end user. In the field of software projects, the notion of project success is divergent among project performance evaluators. External stakeholders focus on budget compliance and deadlines while internal stakeholders will focus more on achieving development goals (Agarwal & Rathod, 2006).

5.2 Artificial intelligence in project management

5.2.1 Introduction to artificial intelligence and its potential

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a discipline that combines a range of sciences and techniques (including computing, mathematics, statistics, etc.) to “present or simulate intelligent behaviour” according to the Oxford English Dictionary. These tasks, which mimic the cognitive abilities of a human, cover a wide range of fields, including problem solving, language comprehension, decision-making and facial or voice recognition.

AI is both a field of scientific research and an interdisciplinary field that raises philosophical, ethical, societal, legal and moral issues. This diversity explains the complexity of identifying a precise, factual and definitive definition of artificial intelligence, since it raises so many questions about the nature of intelligence and the relationship between man and machine.

Table 2: Main difficulties in defining artificial intelligence

Obstacles	Description
Complexity of the notion of intelligence	Intelligence is a multidimensional concept, encompassing cognitive processes such as reasoning, understanding, learning and problem solving. Perceptions of intelligence differ from one individual to another and from one cultural context to another.
AI is constantly evolving	Artificial intelligence is continually being redefined as IT systems and technologies evolve. What is once considered advanced AI can become ordinary as new discoveries are made.
Diversity of AI approaches and techniques	There are a variety of methods for creating AI, with different techniques following their own principles and rules.

The complexity of defining intelligence is highlighted by the Oxford English Dictionary, which gives several perspectives, including that of “the ability to understand, the intellect” which encompasses the ability to grasp intellectual concepts, as well as that of an act of mental understanding, in particular a rational” which evokes a being endowed with reason.

The constant evolution of AI paves the way for the democratisation of certain uses in a quest for competitiveness and the stimulation of innovation. However, we are far from having reached maturity in this field. This is illustrated by the small amount of available data being exploited by AI in business, despite the growth in data generated, which is a source of complexity for businesses. Initiating work with AI is crucial for improving the value perceived by clients, employees or other stakeholders, but does not guarantee the maintenance of a competitive advantage, due to the speed of its evolution (Meline, 2023).

5.2.2 The evolution of artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence has a history dating back to the 1940s, when technological advances were stimulated by the Second World War in a desire to understand how machines could imitate the way humans worked (Council of Europe, n.d.).

It was around the 1950s that the foundations of AI were laid following the “Turing test” drawn up by the mathematician Alan Turing. This studied whether a programme could think like a human being or merely imitate one, and whether it was possible to distinguish between them (Costanza Mariani and Mauro Mancini, 2023). The first mention of the term “artificial intelligence” and its popularisation came from the lecture at Dartmouth College in 1956 by John McCarthy (Professor at Princeton, Stanford and MIT), during which researchers had to define the foundations of artificial intelligence and possible areas of future work. This event marked the start of international collaboration in the field.

In the 1980s-1990s, interest and investment in artificial intelligence fluctuated in a period known as the “AI winter”. Persistent challenges such as the lack of computing power limited the capabilities of artificial intelligence in terms of efficiency and speed, leading to a decline in investment in research. Historically, public interest in AI has fluctuated, with periods of excitement and popularity following technological advances and periods of stagnation or decline when progress was slow, limited and costly (Costanza Mariani and Mauro Mancini, 2023).

In the 1990s and 2000s, high-profile public successes boosted funding for AI, as when IBM's Deep Blue AI (a multinational IT technology and services company) defeated the reigning world chess champion in 1997. Or when DeepMind's AI AlphaGo (a Google subsidiary) won against the world champion in the game of Go in 2017. In 2023, the AI was beaten by a human amateur at the game of Go, who had the help of another computer to identify a flaw.

Between 2010 and 2021, AI experienced spectacular growth, as shown by the increase in scientific publications on AI, which more than doubled (to over 500,000), and the filing of patents for inventions designed by AI, which increased 30-fold between 2015 and 2021. An additional highlight is the increase in the number of users contributing to open source AI software libraries, reflecting a growing interest in AI (Stanford University, 2023; Wang, 2019). Complementing individuals, growing political interest in AI is demonstrated by a 6.5-fold increase in mentions of artificial intelligence in global legislative proceedings since 2016 (Stanford University, 2023).

In the 2020s, AI was democratized among the general public with internet access. Previously the preserve of scientists and businesses, it is now being used by individuals, as it is easy to use, cheaper or even free, and freely accessible. The main areas of interest are text and image generation, question response and programming assistance.

The expansion of AI is influenced by a so-called “black box” effect regarding its opacity and lack of explainability. The input and output data are identifiable, but the internal workings and influences on the result remain unclear in many cases due to their complexity. This problem has a direct impact on data protection, security, ethics and legal issues. This is particularly true in the fields of healthcare for patient diagnosis, finance for loans, criminal justice, and the security of countries or individuals, for example with autonomous vehicles.

The important aspects are:

- The key to understanding this is to be able to identify how things work, anticipate faults and improve performance and robustness.
- The key to accountability: being able to define who is responsible for the operation and effects, and being able to assume this responsibility.

Figure 6: Milestones in the development of artificial intelligence

Source: <https://supertilt.fr/ia-des-origines-a-lere-chatgpt/>

AI is present in many aspects of everyday life such as medical diagnostics in laboratories, machine translation, content recommendation on streaming platforms, advertising targeting or autonomous vehicles. Artificial intelligence is integrated into objects such as computers, smartphones, vehicles, connected objects, etc.

Artificial intelligence in the field of project management has been present for some time but for a minority of project managers. AI is used as a personal assistant or as a team of consultants who can provide advice and perform tasks on projects. Currently 21% of Project Managers use AI in project management always or often. This use will expand thanks to the support of senior management, 82% of whom say that AI will have an impact on the execution of future projects in the next five years (PMI, 2023.) Project management practices are undergoing major transformations and will be radically different by 2030 compared to the way they were in 2017 (Van Der Meulen, 2017).

5.2.3 Machine Learning in Project Management

The Oxford English Dictionary defines Machine Learning (ML) as “the ability of computers to learn and adapt without following explicit instructions, using algorithms and statistical models to analyse and infer patterns in data.” In other words, ML mimics the ability of human learning, gradually adapting and improving without programming thanks to algorithms that learn from existing data and iteratively improve their accuracy (Costanza Mariani and Mauro Mancini, 2023).

Machine Learning is commonly found in everyday applications such as digital advertising targeting, medical diagnostics in the healthcare sector and voice or facial recognition systems (Christensson, 2019). Thanks to its ability to identify trends and patterns, ML is effective in applications such as fraud detection, property price prediction and spam filters for email.

The optimal approach to integrating artificial intelligence into project management is the use of Machine Learning (Wang, 2019). Applied to project management, ML is revolutionising data collection and analysis automation, real-time report generation such as project progress and resource planning (Nieto-Rodriguez, 2023). Another added value of machine learning is the ability to predict project trends in terms of time and budget (Wang, 2019). These functions make it easier to select projects by comparing them with historical data on projects at different levels of maturity and formalism: active, completed, cancelled, in the design stage, in proposal (Washington, 2023). In case of actual use, we can see that ML improves conversational agents, becoming a true assistant available without time or calendar restrictions for the project team to answer questions, guide on the use of project management software or advise on processes (Washington, 2023).

To sum up, there are several levels at which Machine Learning can be used in project management:

- Analysing data and generating reports on project progress;
- Resource allocation management;
- Risk management;
- Planning, to prioritise tasks.

Progress in project management will be more visible and radical when there is widespread adoption of these growing offerings of AI tools tailored to project management (Nieto-Rodriguez, 2023).

5.2.3.1 Deep Learning in Project Management

The Oxford Learner's Dictionary defines Deep Learning (DP), or Deep Learning, a subdomain of Machine Learning, as “a type of artificial intelligence in which computers designed to function similarly to the human brain repeatedly process huge amounts of data in order to learn information. Deep learning mimics how humans acquire knowledge”. This technology resembles the network structure of neurons in the human brain with many layers of data processing.

Deep learning is relevant in several areas that involve problems related to our senses and expressions such as facial recognition, machine translation or speech synthesis.

5.2.3.2 Generative AI in project management

Generative Artificial Intelligence, also known as GenAI, is a branch of Deep Learning that allows the creation of content such as images, text, videos or music. Its content is based on existing data and on precise indications of the elements to be taken into account, such as context or words (Härilin et al., 2023). It can be used for a variety of purposes, such as product design, video game creation, artistic creation, etc.

Figure 7: Summary of generative AI

Source: <https://supertilt.fr/ia-des-origines-a-lere-chatgpt/>

Generative AI is marked by a new realism that seems to be produced by humans, especially for the generation of text, code, video, image or audio. One of the elements of value creation is the improvement of process efficiency by reducing human intervention, particularly through automation (Deloitte, 2023). The first functions where Generative AI creates value are IT (code generation), marketing and sales operations (creation of content in various forms, personalisation, market and client research), customer service (conversational agents) and product development (prototyping, pace of development, time-to-market) (Deloitte, 2023; Härlin et al., 2023).

With the growth in the use of chatbots and text and video generation systems, generative AI has gained visibility in the public consciousness since the 2020s (Stanford University, 2023). Generative AI has received a great deal of media attention by winning prizes in artistic competitions and competing with human candidates in the Bar exam, obtaining scores close to those of the most talented candidates (Härlin et al., 2023).

In project management, there are three levels of use of generative artificial intelligence:

- The automation of simple and time-consuming tasks, without the need for validation by the Project Manager. For example, generating progress reports or analysing documents.
- Assistance with simple, controlled tasks requiring verification of accuracy and precision by the project manager. For example, to draw up an action plan or complete an analysis.
- Extended assistance on complex and strategic tasks requiring the use of AI on specific tasks. For example, making decisions with numerous interdependencies and variables (PMI, 2023).

5.2.3.3 NLP in project management

Webopedia defines Natural Language Processing (NLP), or automatic processing of natural language in French, as a branch of Machine Learning that "deals with the analysis, understanding and generation of languages that humans naturally use in order to interface with computers in written and spoken contexts using natural human languages instead of computer languages" (Webopedia, 2021). NLP deals with written or spoken human language, regardless of dialect, accent, intonation, grammatical or spelling errors, use of homonyms, metaphors or expressions.

NLP deals with natural language understanding (spoken words, syntactic and semantic analysis, context of the utterance), automatic language translation, text and graphics generation, response to written or verbal commands, sentiment analysis (text, oral discourse, social networks), conversational agents, spam detection, etc.

Figure 8: NLP summary

Source: <https://amazon.com/insights/what-is-nlp-and-how-it-is-implemented-in-our-lives/>

By understanding human language, NLP analyses unstructured data such as project documents, conversations (business messaging, chat messages, speech, videos) to perform administrative and planning tasks and improve communication. The main areas to be optimised are project prioritisation, the generation and tracking of project documentation, automated testing tools and the overall tasks of project management offices (Nieto-Rodriguez and Vargas, 2023).

6 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

6.1 Semi-structured interviews

Research is based on a qualitative approach through semi-structured interviews. An interview guide was drawn up prior to the interview and included ten open-ended questions organised by theme. We first announced the subject of the research and the themes of the interview guide to the interviewees during the scheduling of the appointments and then we reminded them of these elements a second time on the day of the interview.

The aim of the semi-structured interviews was to obtain an in-depth understanding of the issue, a diversity of perspectives and contextualisation by gathering individual opinions and perceptions and accounts of situations.

In order to obtain detailed and nuanced results, we conducted ten individual semi-structured interviews, using an established framework with questions formulated in an interview guide, while preserving the adaptability of the exchange according to the development of the interviewee's ideas.

Participants were interviewed between May and July 2024. The interviews, whether in person or by videoconference, were not recorded but were entered manually in the form of interview notes. Each interview was conducted in one-hour sessions. For more details on the interviews, the transcripts can be found in the appendices.

6.2 Stakeholder profiles

This study aims to represent a diversity of profiles in terms of professions, experience and skills in order to obtain a broad vision of artificial intelligence applied to project management.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT EXPERIENCE

BREAKDOWN OF PARTICIPANTS' MAIN JOB SECTORS

BREAKDOWN OF YEARS OF EXPERIENCE

DISTRIBUTION OF AI SPECIALISTS

The study was carried out with a panel of respondents from a variety of positions, and the composition is fairly balanced. A third are innovation or data management professionals who play a key role in the development of technologies and the exploitation of data in their company, and a third are consultants providing their expertise for corporate clients. The consultants work in the fields of project management, management and digital transformation, carrying out projects for clients in a

wide range of sectors. CEOs or Founders, who are the strategic decision-makers, represent 22% of participants, while project management professionals account for 11% of those interviewed.

Participating companies range from freelancers to global multinationals, providing a diversity of professional environments. Participants work in various sectors: food, energy, pharmaceuticals, software publishing. Participants working in IT and business services and consultancy operate in a variety of sectors on behalf of their clients, such as energy or pharmaceuticals.

The diversity of backgrounds is high, with a strong presence of established professionals, with 15 years' experience or more (61%), and a balanced representation of young professionals and career backgrounds, with an equal proportion of 14% of participants having less than 5 years' experience, between 5 and 10 years, and between 10 and 15 years.

43% of participants have a second job in addition to their main job as Speakers, Educators or Influencers on social networks in artificial intelligence, which reveals their expertise in this field and their ability to influence it.

6.3 Strengths and weaknesses of the study

6.3.1 Strengths

The sample was diverse in terms of professional background, business sector, experience, knowledge of AI, which enabled the results to represent a variety of perspectives and a depth of knowledge.

The methodology mobilises academic skills and knowledge with concepts and methods and professional skills derived from practical contributions linked to the environments and players. The methodology combines several methods, including a literature review and qualitative interviews.

This topic, which is rarely addressed in the literature and is fairly recent, is becoming the focus of networking groups, communities and events among project management professionals.

6.3.2 Weaknesses

In the case of our research, there is a volunteer bias since the participants were informed of the subject of the study beforehand, which may have influenced their decision to take part. It is conceivable that those who accepted had an interest in the subject and potentially possessed a deeper view of the application of AI compared to the majority of professionals.

The qualitative semi-structured interviews we conducted generated detailed data providing insights into the perceptions, opinions and experiences of the participants. Nevertheless, the results are based on a restricted sample, which may limit the extent to which our conclusions can be generalised, and this corresponds to sampling bias.

Another potential bias is geographical bias because all our participants are French and French-speaking. However, some work in large international groups with a globalised internal culture.

Intervention bias exists because the interviews were conducted, transcribed and analysed by the same individual. In practice, it was not feasible for three different people to each perform one of the three stages in order to strengthen the validity of the study.

7 RESEARCH RESULTS

7.1 Results

The results are organised into 4 main themes and presented in a neutral manner without interpretation:

- Impacts of AI on project management methods and processes;
- Correlation between business strategy and the success of AI-enabled projects;
- Impacts of AI on the labour market and project management jobs;
- From the AI Assistant to the evolution of Project Manager skills.

7.1.1 Impacts of AI on project management methods and processes

Figure 9: Modernising project management processes with AI

THEMATICS	SAMPLES OF EXPERT OPINIONS
<p>ACCESSIBILITY OF PROJECT METHODOLOGIES</p>	<p>“Project management is not innate and requires specific skills that not everyone has. It requires subjectivity and human relationships, so AI will remove the method but will be able to help by advising on it.”</p> <p>“In the short term, certifications are very important because AI is a new technology so confidence relies on Project Managers' knowledge and certifications. In the medium to long term, if there is a move away from project certifications then this could undermine the ability for human control over the machine.”</p>
<p>AUTOMATION OF TASKS</p>	<p>“So tasks that shouldn't originally be human tasks like organising project logistics and scheduling are going to be automated.”</p> <p>“In the medium term the nuclear core of project management is going to be automated and taken over entirely by AI. These virtual agents will be able to execute complete project management processes without human intervention.”</p> <p>“AI offers the following main benefits in project management: time saving with the automation of repetitive tasks, simplified task planning, information synthesis, improved communication, maintaining agenda consistency.”</p>
<p>EVOLUTION OF EFFICIENCY CRITERIA</p>	<p>“In reality, the same AI will not produce the same results if it is not used or mastered in the same way by two employees. A Project Manager with a good command of AI can improve costs, quality and timescales, but it's no guarantee of staying within budget or meeting deadlines.”</p> <p>“With the integration of AI, the project manager's work will be more qualitative and rapid. The notions of client satisfaction, communication and feedback solicited at the end of the project could be important evaluation criteria.”</p>

The results of the research indicate that artificial intelligence is perceived as a structuring and simplifying tool for project management. Professionals see AI as a way of making a procedural domain more accessible and facilitating the use of these methods. AI will greatly improve the management of simple projects, in particular by verifying the accuracy and quality of the information entered in the structuring project management deliverables used.

This will be particularly beneficial for those new to project management by providing structured support and effective methods. In addition, the transfer of knowledge from an ongoing project or feedback from a completed project appears to be a key progression in project management with AI.

These technologies will make it easier to structure the collection of documentation and improve the sharing of knowledge, with significant impacts on the training and integration of new players in the project, making them operational more quickly.

AI speeds up task completion and improves quality, while ensuring compliance with the project management methodologies established by the company. Opinions differ on the scope of tasks that can be automated. Some professionals believe that AI's perfect knowledge of methods will enable it to handle all planning and logistics tasks, making project management certifications obsolete. One way of thinking is that the more technical and decomposable a task is, as in project management methodologies, the easier it is to automate, or even to have it carried out completely by AI.

The other experts, who are in the majority, say that AI will never be able to fully replace human interaction and the subjectivity required for project management. Providing answers on project methodology is different from putting it into practice on a daily basis. They see AI as a support and consultancy tool requiring human supervision to guarantee the reliability and adaptability of methods and to challenge algorithms. The majority of experts rule out calling into question the learning of methods, believing that abandoning this technicality would reduce the capacity for human control over AI. The complexity of the methods could become even more confusing for stakeholders if AI is the sole source of knowledge.

The expansion of hybrid project management and the dynamics of experienced professionals adapting and combining the tools of several methodologies according to needs and context, seem to be decisive for the preservation of technical expertise. A significant part of the Project Manager's job consists of identifying and interpreting needs and the corresponding use cases. This decision to adapt, with its share of intuition linked to experience and the consideration of weak signals within a limited information framework, constitutes one of the added values of the human element in this field. Some experts consider traditional project management methods to be outdated, as they no longer meet the strategic needs of modern project managers, who are now focused on strategy rather than execution. This transformation is attributed to digitalisation rather than AI.

Experts are converging on the medium-term democratisation of the automation of planning and steering tasks by AI, considered to be the current core of project management. These virtual agents will coordinate entire processes without human intervention, and time-consuming technical tasks with low or medium added value for humans will be taken over. Professionals are talking about a reallocation to the machine of tasks that should not be assigned to humans. However, the experts insist on the need for human control and adjustments to ensure the right fit with the context.

Opinions on the evolution of efficiency criteria in project management differ with regard to the cost-quality-time triptych. Some professionals consider the iron triangle to be an unshakeable pillar of project performance evaluation, while others see it as just one element among others, such as indicators of commercial value and corporate strategy. A minority of experts believe that these criteria have become obsolete since the advent of innovative methodologies such as Effectuation or Design Thinking, which focus on the value perceived by stakeholders and innovation rather than strict adherence to costs, quality and deadlines.

Opinions on the evolution of efficiency criteria in project management are also divided. Some professionals see the cost-quality-time triptych as an indestructible foundation, while others suggest that these criteria are already outdated without the integration of AI, replaced by indicators linked to business value and innovation. It is the increased efficiency of AI in terms of cost management, quality of deliverables and improved compliance with deadlines that is raising questions about the evolution of the criteria. Risk management is becoming fundamental to assessing the dangers associated with the use of AI as the project progresses, in order to determine whether the results are acceptable in relation to the risks incurred. Evaluation criteria that are usually reserved for the end of the project, such as client satisfaction and communication, could play a more important role

In conclusion, AI improves efficiency by automating repetitive and technical tasks and optimising planning, but requires human control to guarantee contextual relevance, for the interpretation of

needs and the intuitive and subjective aspects of projects. The results of our research show that AI in project management improves efficiency by automating repetitive tasks and optimising planning, while requiring human control to ensure contextual relevance. Opinions differ on the long-term impact on traditional project management methodologies, but a consensus is emerging on time savings and process simplification.

7.1.2 Synergies between business strategy and project success with AI

Figure 10: AI in project management and strategy, an alliance for sustainable performance

THEMATICS	SAMPLES OF EXPERT OPINIONS
MISSION AND VISION	<p>"A project is doomed to failure from the outset if it is not aligned with a clear strategy, objectives in line with the company's mission and vision, and a real need on the part of customers or society. Companies spend a lot of energy trying to put human and financial resources back into projects that shouldn't have been launched in the first place. All possible AI solutions can be put in place if the decision to launch the project is not the right one, then AI will not change anything. AI will help optimise time management, quality and problem solving but it can't change a project's flawed strategic viability and uncertainties."</p>
MARKET POSITION	<p>"Competitive pressure will drive the use of AI which will drive productivity and margin gains for companies, leading to increased competitive pressure and therefore accelerating the development of AI technologies."</p> <p>"Everyone will eventually have access to this AI, so what will make the difference will be those who know how to use it effectively. Some will use it in a basic way as a search engine instead of Google, and others will fully exploit its predictive and prescriptive capabilities which will give them a competitive advantage."</p>
INTERNAL POLICIES	<p>"For internal projects, there is the need for sufficient incentive to drive AI adoption that can be illustrated by the "donkey and carrot" metaphor. This can equate to a financial, career advantage, or very effective communication about the benefits of using AI by tangibly demonstrating the potential benefits individually and by project."</p> <p>"Any transformation, especially with AI, must emphasise collaboration with social partners. Management support is political, and the social partners have a crucial role in removing reluctance. Their support is essential to effectively identify fears and represent employees' needs."</p>

Our results highlight the integration of AI, which must be aligned with the company's mission and vision. It is important for management to understand the importance of AI and its uses, and to support this technological and behavioural shift. The successful adoption of AI in project management must be based on a clear strategic vision and recognition of the urgency to change in order to trigger the transformation, as Kotter's model highlights. A project fails because of a lack of strategic alignment, an inconsistency between the objectives and the company's mission, or a poorly qualified need on the part of clients or the company. AI can optimise management, but it cannot correct the strategic viability of a project that is unviable from the outset, and therefore the waste of resources allocated to it.

Experts point out that if AI forecasts or predictions about projects are incomprehensible to policymakers then their strategic value is zero. This so-called "black box" effect underlines the need to improve the AI knowledge and skills of all employees, at all levels of the hierarchy.

According to the opinions of professionals, a company's competitive position and market share will be impacted by the integration of AI into project management. Automating and simplifying processes increases productivity, intensifying competitive pressure. Companies that adopt AI quickly can

position themselves advantageously in the market, while those that delay risk appearing to be lagging behind in their industry.

The increasing deployment of conversational agents seems to be a strategic necessity, even if this adoption remains for the moment exploratory by business area rather than globalised. The sales, marketing, communication, human resources and finance functions are the first to be affected. The mobilisation of a wide range of skills in a single day for a project manager makes it difficult to manage all tasks simultaneously using AI technology.

The regular use of conversational agents by employees remains in the minority, perceived by some as a gadget that cannot be easily integrated into everyday activities. Opinions differ on the types of employees who are active consumers of AI: in some companies, it is mainly senior experts who are adopting it, while in other companies it is mainly the younger generation.

To successfully adopt AI, companies need to establish clear and shared internal policies on confidentiality and cybersecurity. A framework that is not overly restrictive is needed to prevent clandestine use by employees.

For external client projects, full resources including training and budget must be provided. If AI is used then it is imperative to provide full resources including training and a budget. For internal projects, the incentive to adopt AI should be to highlight use cases of previous project management practices that could have been improved by AI.

For internal projects, it is important to show concrete cases where AI has improved results, as well as offering financial benefits and career prospects to motivate project managers. Financial benefits and career prospects can motivate project managers to embrace AI and reduce the reticence associated with jeopardising previously operational project management processes. One of the obstacles perceived by professionals is the lack of an instinct to use AI in their daily work when an opportunity arises.

In conclusion, the results of the study show that the integration of AI into project management must be in line with the company's strategy if it is to succeed. Management understanding and support is essential, as is understanding that AI will not be able to guarantee the viability of a project and correct fundamental alignment errors. Early adoption of AI in project management can offer a significant competitive advantage provided internal policies including privacy and cybersecurity and suitable means of adoption are put in place.

7.1.3 Impacts of AI on the project management labour market

Figure 11: Impacts of artificial intelligence on the labour market

THEMATICS	SAMPLES OF EXPERT OPINIONS
<p>SYSTEMIC TRANSFORMATION</p>	<p>“The impact of AI is systemic with a global transformation of the world of work, the institution of work, which will ravage the world of work as we know it today in the next ten years.”</p> <p>“With the evolution of AI we are going to be faced with major social problems, unlike other industrial revolutions. Competitive pressure will drive the use of AI, which will make companies more productive and increase their margins, leading to an increase in competitive pressure and therefore accelerating the development of AI technologies.”</p>
<p>PLACE OF THE HUMAN</p>	<p>“Automation can optimise productivity by saving several working days and full-time equivalents (FTEs).”</p> <p>“Project Manager jobs are not going to disappear, but will benefit from additional support. AI cannot completely replace humans because you need someone to blame for errors or biases and without a Project Manager, it is impossible to find someone to blame for problems between the Middle Manager, the Programmer, the Software or the company implementing the AI.”</p>
<p>PERCEPTION OF AI</p>	<p>“Artificial intelligence is nothing new, and today it has been reduced to generative AI, even though it has been around for years, particularly for data analysis or on-board computing for automotive sensors.”</p> <p>“Algorithms are a form of AI that has significant potential to complement humans, but the general public must not forget the advances that have been made over the years in AI other than this.”</p>
<p>PRIVATE USE</p>	<p>“People’s habits when it comes to searching for data are changing. They seem to prefer to use conversational agents outside the workplace for data search, compared to traditional internet search methods, because of the speed and quality of the results.”</p> <p>“The previously stated problematic behaviours where employees will use AI on their personal time with company data, which can be sensitive, to improve their work as this is not allowed within the company framework and during their working hours.”</p>

Our results show that the impacts of AI on the labour market and project management jobs elicit varied opinions among respondents. AI is often perceived as something new because of generative AI, but it has been around for years in areas such as data analysis and embedded computing. These historical advances are at the root of current progress, and the perception of what AI is evolves over time as computing capacities, technological advances and society evolve. Functionalities that were once considered AI, such as algorithms or simple parametric methods for robots, are now considered basic. For the years 2020-2025, AI is represented more by large language models (LLMs), which are highly effective in administrative and support functions such as project management.

Our investigations show that the democratisation of AI will lead to a systemic transformation of the world of work, redefining the nature of employment. The technical dimension of work will be diminished by automation in favour of the human dimension. This transition is seen as a positive opportunity, although the difficulty is greater than previous digital and societal transformations, such as the rise of the Internet. The current model of work does not meet human aspirations. Technologies will replace certain jobs requiring a high level of technical expertise, while jobs requiring human support will be upgraded.

With the widespread adoption of the Internet, individuals have had to learn to use new tools, but the core of the transformation remains focused on technical skills. In the case of artificial intelligence, the effects on human dimensions require personal development, changes in behaviour and

mentalities. These parameters are ingrained, which makes the process more complex and slows it down.

The experts reveal that artificial intelligence will not immediately transform all professions because of the attachment to traditional values, habits and the financial and security issues facing companies. The integration of AI into processes will take place gradually, with gradual changes.

A consensus is emerging on the significant savings in human resources brought about by artificial intelligence, reducing the need to hire additional staff or call on external consultants. AI performs tasks that would otherwise require several days' work. The majority of professionals consider that AI is not in competition with employees. And although some jobs are disappearing and others will emerge, decision-makers wishing to take the path of AI must value employee support rather than seeking to reduce staff numbers.

The observations are consistent with slight variations in the potential replacement of humans by AI among project management professionals. In the long run, it is possible that project management will be almost fully automated with virtual agents running complete processes without human intervention. Artificial intelligence will serve more as a support for the human rather than a competitor or replacement because of the need to assign human responsibilities. Supervision for high-stakes decisions and bias management limits complete automation. Moreover, individuals do not seem ready to be led by artificial intelligences. If a company finds that project managers can be replaced by AI to manage the project, then their skills should be called into question, according to some of the specialists in our study.

The study shows that job trends are directly influenced by developments in the use of artificial intelligence in the private sector. Some professionals use AI on a daily basis outside the workplace for purposes such as sector or technology monitoring, creative production (design, music), the use of virtual agents to organise schedules for non-business activities or personal communication management. AI has evolved data search habits, which are simplified compared to traditional methods because of the speed and quality of results. Operational optimisation in the private sphere seems to be gradually changing expectations in the corporate world.

What the experts are saying is that artificial intelligence, perceived as something new because of generative AI, is an area that is constantly evolving. Business expectations are evolving as individuals integrate AI into their private lives. The democratisation of AI will lead to a systemic transformation of the world of work, diminishing the technical dimension in favour of strategic and human dimensions. AI acting as an Assistant rather than a substitute for the Project Manager.

7.1.4 From virtual Assistant to Project Manager as augmented human

Figure 12: Human-AI duo, an evolution in the skills and role of the Project Manager

THEMATICS	SAMPLES OF EXPERT OPINIONS
<p>AI AS AN ASSISTANT OR COGNITIVE EXPANSION</p>	<p>"The use of AI raises ethical issues, such as the possibility of prompting being considered as a form of cheating. Project managers need to know how and when to use AI ethically to ensure the integrity of project management."</p> <p>"AI facilitates communication and coordination between people who don't speak the same technical language. Sharing information from a technical team to a business team is difficult and essential in project management because it is the core business of the project manager. AI simplifies this link by making a big step forward."</p>
<p>CRITICAL THINKING</p>	<p>"AI is very powerful so it's easy to take its results at face value. This can lead to dehumanisation through the exacerbated standardisation of tasks. It is important to retain intellectual independence and a critical mind."</p> <p>"Each AI model is parameterised to provide an answer, which can lead to erroneous or hallucinatory results."</p>
<p>IMPACTS ON SKILLS</p>	<p>"For complex projects where you have to get teams who don't know each other to work together, human coordination is essential. It is the added value of the Project Manager to carry out this hard work and put these collective efforts to music, so AI is not going to replace him or her in this respect."</p> <p>"The functions of Project Managers will evolve and they will be expected to step up their skills and focus on strategic aspects because that's where their expertise is really needed."</p> <p>"First and foremost, you need to have competent Project Managers who know about project management. If a Project Manager doesn't master their project and uses incorrect data then AI is only going to deliver incorrect and inefficient results."</p>

Our study reveals that project management professionals consider AI to be a successful personal assistant for carrying out their role. AI is perceived as a tool that supports human efforts and increases the capabilities of the Project Manager, in other words as a cognitive expansion that would make superhumans.

AI's ability to break down a project into small stages and levels of technicality enables it to promote the autonomy of the parties involved and fluid communication between different teams with different specialities. AI facilitates this transfer of information between technical and business-oriented stakeholders, the core responsibilities of the Project Manager. It is imperative for the project management professional to keep their knowledge up to date, which often depends on internal or external experts who may be unavailable, expensive, or sometimes incomprehensible.

Delegating project communication tasks to AI makes it possible to establish the immediacy of information, reduce communication times and increase efficiency. For example, a conversational agent providing real-time information allows executive committee members to make decisions at the right time.

The majority of professionals consider that AI, although effective for delegated tasks, requires supervision and adjustments on the part of the project manager for complex or high value-added subjects, just as they would with a human assistant. The reluctance to delegate power to a machine is a brake for Project Managers.

The use of AI raises divergent ethical questions about skills, in particular prompting, which is seen by some professionals as a form of fraud and dishonesty with regard to real skills, and by others as

a demonstration of the optimisation of work by the individual. To ensure the integrity of project management, our results suggest that it is imperative that project managers use AI ethically.

Our research findings highlight the need to maintain human creativity and innovation by using AI as an assistance tool rather than a standalone technology. AI does not excel at serendipity unlike humans i.e. the ability to generate innovative ideas using elements from one domain in another as it is not programmed to make creative associations beyond what is requested. Although AI facilitates continuous learning, over-reliance without solid project management training will lead to standardisation of projects and harm innovation, compromising competitive advantage.

Experts stress the importance of maintaining a critical mind when faced with artificial intelligences that follow a pre-existing model, which is sometimes ill-suited to the constraints of the market and the project. Furthermore, the accuracy of AI is re-examined in the event of “hallucinations”: if AI generates incorrect information, the cognitive biases derived from data annotated by humans and the programming of AI aim to provide a different response. While the integration of AI into certain professions such as project management may have a moderate impact in the event of failure, others such as finance or healthcare do not have the same level of risk acceptance.

The power of artificial intelligence encourages certain professionals who are insufficiently educated in its uses and abuses to accept these results without question. Dependence on the results generated will lead to progressive dehumanisation and a loss of intellectual independence. However, our study seems to show that project management professionals are not ready to follow AI recommendations indiscriminately.

Professionals agree that the main threat to the use of AI in project management is the lack of project management skills among professionals. Many project managers do not have adequate training to provide them with a solid foundation and the necessary methodological input. Our feedback also indicates that Project Managers are actually doing PMO work on a daily basis. Integrating artificial intelligence without filling these gaps in project management could exacerbate the failure rate of corporate projects.

If a project manager does not master their project and uses AI with inaccurate data, then the results will be erroneous and ineffective, because AI needs to feed off a quality base in order to be competent. For example, if project meetings are not properly prepared, without a clear objective or with incoherent ideas presented, then AI will not be able to improve the situation. However, our study reveals that some skills gaps between Project Managers will tend to be erased on project communication and monitoring through AI that will reduce the pitfalls of poorly transmitted or misunderstood messages depending on the audience.

Before the widespread adoption of AI tools in project management, it is essential to optimise the use of current project management tools. A large proportion of companies do not have project management tools or do not use them effectively, concentrating on structuring cost and financial management rather than planning. Before artificial intelligence can be used, project management professionals need to be trained in the use of existing tools. However, research shows that, according to experts, the most effective project managers are not necessarily those who are best equipped technologically. Efficient project management professionals are those who excel in communication and interaction with teams.

Thanks to the time saved by AI, professionals can develop their skills where AI will not intervene such as decision-making, coordinating experts from different specialities and conflict management. The role of the project manager is to work together with individuals who are not used to or willing to collaborate, that is to say, a strategic activity that AI cannot replace. Interpersonal skills and the ability to provide leadership to encourage collective efforts are specific to humans.

The work shows consensus on the need for project management professionals to train in the use of AI to properly interact with its tools, and specifically prompt engineering. Having AI skills is no longer reserved for IT or data science profiles. The effectiveness of the AI result depends heavily on the user's language skills, ability to make a precise request and the extent of their vocabulary. For less

competent individuals, it will be necessary to improve oral expression or focus on AI functionalities that favour verbal exchanges. The efficiency of the project also depends on the level of AI expertise. A project manager can use AI to improve costs, quality and deadlines, but this does not guarantee that the budget or deadlines will be met. Using AI as an assistant is akin to managing a human assistant, in that the project manager may find it difficult to work well with it.

In the medium term, when AI is integrated into the majority of software publishers, the difference between a high-performing or under-performing project manager will depend on his or her ability to make full use of AI's predictive and prescriptive capabilities. What's more, describing and formalising the problem to be solved for prompting already enables the requester to become more autonomous in solving it through a process of mental reflection.

In conclusion, our study reveals that project management professionals view AI as a powerful personal assistant that increases the value of their project and their individual abilities as a cognitive extension. AI facilitates the fragmentation of projects into stages that can be automated and encourages the autonomy of technology. However, human supervision remains essential for complex and strategic tasks and to ensure ethical use. The interpersonal, creative and decision-making skills of the project manager remain irreplaceable, and AI technologies need to be developed in conjunction with human skills.

7.2 Discussion

7.2.1 Modelling of the main results and correlation with the literature review

The results of our study show that artificial intelligence in project management arouses diverse opinions but highlights a consensus on an evolution on four main themes with the use of AI: the labour market and project management jobs, synergy with corporate strategy, project management processes and the skills and role of the Project Manager.

Figure 13: Artificial intelligence issues for project management

The literature review confirms our findings on potential major labour market disruptions. AI has the potential to replace up to a quarter of current professional tasks with automation, corresponding to 300 million full-time jobs, or around two-thirds of jobs in the United States and Europe (Hatzius et al., 2023). Many concerns relate to the risk of job losses and the fear of failure to adopt AI technologies due to their complexity and fear of the unknown. The replacement of humans with AI is already visible, jobs in the technical sectors have been replaced by automation and conversational agents (Wang, 2019; Fridgeirsson et al., 2021). Cost may explain this trend, as acquiring AI

technology by licence, for example, is economically more attractive than recruiting an in-house or outsourced employee (Lowe et al., 2016).

Figure 14: AI adoption and annual employee productivity growth

Source: Goldman Sachs Global Investment Research

Source: https://www.key4biz.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Global-Economics-Analyst_-The-Potentially-Large-Effects-of-Artificial-Intelligence-on-Economic-Growth-Briggs_Kodnani.pdf

This illustration shows that according to academic studies, employees who adopt AI will be able to have an annual productivity increase of 2 to 3 percentage points, with an average of 3.1% and a median of 2.6%. This is not modest and could lead to economic gains, wage increases and higher living standards for the individuals concerned.

However, the majority of positions and sectors are only partially vulnerable to automation and are more likely to be assisted by AI than to be replaced. In the United States, 7% of jobs are in danger of being replaced by AI, 63% could benefit from AI support as an assistant, and 30% would remain unaffected (Hatzius et al., 2023). By extension, increasing automation could not reduce jobs but rather multiply them because by freeing up time for more challenging tasks, it decreases turnover and stimulates innovation (Lowe et al., 2016).

AI has the potential to foster the creation of new project management jobs focused on AI exploitation and data science (PMI, 2023; Wang, 2019; Mariani and Mancini, 2023). For example for data cleaning and analysis, system maintenance, algorithm development, security and legal expertise.

The results of our operational impact study are complemented by a survey of 81 experienced project management professionals which predicts that AI will have a significant impact on critical and procedural areas (cost, time, risk) leading to increased simplification and practicality of project management regardless of professional experience.

Figure 15: Effects of AI on project management in the next 10 years

The PMBOK Knowledge Areas	The Effect on Managing the Knowledge Areas					
	Don't know	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high
1 Integration	14%	4%	19%	26%	30%	7%
2 Scope	15%	3%	23%	26%	27%	6%
3 Schedule	16%	0%	10%	23%	37%	14%
4 Cost	13%	1%	5%	23%	40%	18%
5 Quality	14%	3%	14%	31%	30%	8%
6 Resource	14%	5%	21%	29%	24%	7%
7 Communication	14%	4%	22%	29%	25%	6%
8 Risk	15%	1%	13%	24%	35%	12%
9 Procurement	18%	1%	13%	31%	28%	9%
10 Stakeholder	16%	9%	27%	27%	18%	3%

Source: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042345>

The results of this study make predictions about the potential impact of AI on areas of project management knowledge, as defined in the PMBOK. These projections may be imprecise and may not materialise due to various factors such as societal and technological developments and different use cases. Participants believe that AI will have a very high or high impact on project cost management, with 58% of votes in favour. This suggests a prospect of cost optimisation through automation and data analysis. The areas likely to be most impacted are schedule management and risk management. On the other hand, participants anticipate that stakeholder management will be the area least influenced by AI. With regard to resource management, opinions are varied, ranging from a low, medium and high effect, which does not allow a clear trend to emerge.

AI can be seen as an effective assistant to Project Managers (Tim Washington, 2023; Wang 2023) by enhancing their operational efficiencies. The challenge is to support them in tasks that are not carried out but have low added value that can be automated or that require in-depth analysis of complex criteria such as resource evaluation. (Tim Washington, 2023).

AI is able to think like humans thanks to cognitive technologies allowing it to progress in understanding and learning to achieve human performance but this still requires human intervention (Lowe et al., 2016). AI cannot be fully compared to human intelligence due to the lack of subjective state and consciousness. It can be seen as a cognitive extension of existing mental abilities according to the “extended mind” theory even if it loses logic with the growth of AI autonomy (Nyholm, 2023).

One of the common causes of project failure is related to the difficulty of managing human interactions. An autonomous AI cannot manage the non-configurable components linked to our unconscious human capacities, the internal compass driven by sensitivity and intuition, making it possible to create a counter-intuitive solution, to guarantee that the ethical course is maintained, and to negotiate and motivate a human with a look (PMI, 2023).

Intensive use of AI with dependency could potentially diminish human intelligence over time, as in the case of the reversal of the steady rise in IQ observed over the 20th century, linked to the use of modern technology. This would not be a loss of intelligence at the level of basic human capacities, because the human brain would have to evolve. It would be more like a moral regression due to a lack of practice in making decisions for ourselves or initiating complex reflections that require us to make full use of our intellectual potential (Nyholm, 2023).

There is a risk of over-reliance on AI based on over-confidence. It is essential to remember that the outputs of AI may not be completely aligned or adapted to the human context and needs such as leadership and values (Barcaui and Monat, 2023). Over-reliance on AI can bias the consideration and evaluation of other people's work through an illusion of intelligence for the person using AI

correctly. They are then artificially intelligent without deserving esteem or valuation (Nyholm, 2023). This phenomenon can have a long-term detrimental effect on the effectiveness of projects. If the decisions taken for the project are based on a biased feeling of trust, then this can lead to errors and impacts. And if there is a technological failure, then the project team could find itself operationally blocked if a key skill is missing, which could impact on the smooth continuity of the project.

Today, the previously common concept of having one job for life has largely disappeared, and the possession of one skill for life is in danger of doing the same. Individuals need to develop their area of expertise regularly and have access to continuous training, so that they can adapt to the pace of change (Lowe et al., 2016). Time-consuming administrative, technical or data-related tasks can easily be replaced by AI (Holzmann et al., 2022; Nieto-Rodriguez and Vargas Ricardo, 2023; Costanza Mariani and Mauro Mancini, 2023), saving time and money.

Figure 16: Project management areas least relevant to AI

Frequency	Knowledge Area	#	Process/Topic	Function
15	Other	48	IP (intellectual property)	Manage innovation
14	Project Resource Management	24	Develop team	Training
14	Project Resource Management	26	Acquire resource	Recruit employees
8	Project Resource Management	25	Manage team	Assess team performance
8	Other	47	Security	Fraud inspection
7	Project Communications Management	27	Plan communication	Plan meetings
7	Project Stakeholder Management	37	Contact list	Create contact list
6	Project Resource Management	22	Knowledge management	Create knowledge maps
6	Other	50	Portfolio	Select projects

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1177/87569728211061779>

This illustration highlights that tasks related to resource management, such as creating a knowledge map, recruitment, training and team performance management, are the least favoured for the application of AI. According to the authors, this is justified by a non-perception of these functions by the Project Managers as part of their main responsibilities but more at an organisational level and as an impact on their work.

Interpersonal skills and leadership are valued as technical tasks continue to be automated, becoming increasingly invaluable. In the PMI talent triangle, AI replaces the technical project management skill set. Project Managers can focus more on human interaction, subject to skill enhancement through AI. By automating tedious and depreciated tasks, employees are redirected towards more fulfilling work, which increases employee well-being (Lowe et al., 2016). The development and management of the project team and the planning and management of stakeholders are two complex processes that have little impact or can be substituted by AI. Technology is not yet a substitute for the human being when it comes to providing moral support to a team member in the event of a problem, practising critical thinking or identifying and engaging the least included stakeholders. This enables project managers to develop their soft skills in communication, conflict resolution and emotional intelligence (Fridgeirsson et al., 2021; Holzmann et al., 2022; PMI, 2023; Mariani and Mancini, 2023).

Project Managers' business acumen improves with the delegation of tasks to AI by gaining skills and a finer understanding of the strategic implications of their work and the business (PMI, 2023; Nieto-Rodriguez and Vargas Ricardo, 2023; Costanza Mariani and Mauro Mancini, 2023; Holzmann et al.,

2022) as well as a focus on high-level stakeholder management. Project management professionals will have to generate value and benefits by implementing the strategy.

AI can support the Project Manager in strategic thinking by detecting invisible connections through their own prism and hierarchical level, provided that it is familiar with strategic models (PMI, 2023). Reassigning tasks and valuing employees goes hand in hand with increased efficiency and greater reliance on the reliability and skills of the human operators involved (Lowes et al., 2016).

7.2.2 Interpretation of results

Our study reveals that the integration of artificial intelligence into project management responds positively to the initial research question of whether AI can improve project efficiency. Our hypotheses have been confirmed with regard to the automation and optimisation of project planning and coordination processes, freeing up time for professionals to concentrate on higher added-value tasks in strategy and human relations management. For example, AI optimises the allocation of financial resources through cost forecasting, which reduces the risk of budget overruns and optimises cost management. In addition, AI facilitates time management by predicting the duration of tasks based on previous projects and optimising production through automation, thereby reducing the risk of delays and cutting costs. The results also highlight the far-reaching transformation of professional roles and practices, with the focus shifting from technology to people. This complementarity between humans and technology shows that to gain in efficiency, AI must be perceived as a support tool and not as a competitor, and must require human supervision. The results show that AI can improve project performance, but requires an adaptation of project managers' skills and work processes.

7.2.3 Comparison with existing literature

Our results are consistent with previous studies suggesting that AI can transform project management practices by increasing operational efficiency. Wang (2019) and Holzmann et al. (2022) demonstrated that AI enables more efficient decision-making by automating repetitive tasks and analysing large amounts of data to detect trends and risks. They pointed out that AI optimises basic project management processes such as planning, cost and risk management. Nieto-Rodriguez (2023) and Mariani & Mancini (2023) proved that this automation and real-time forecasting and recommendations frees up time for project managers to focus on strategic and decision-making tasks.

Our study adds a new dimension by exploring the challenges of strategic alignment, human supervision and ethical concerns, which are less addressed in the existing literature. However, our study goes further by highlighting the challenges of thoughtful integration into project management practices, an aspect less addressed in the existing literature. Furthermore, our results show that AI allows the inclusion of new effectiveness criteria in addition to the traditional iron triangle (cost, quality, timelines) to include the perceived value of stakeholders, which better corresponds to modern project management requirements.

7.2.4 Operational recommendations and consequences

- A. **Ensure strategic alignment:** it is important to ensure that the integration of artificial intelligence into project management is aligned with the company's strategic objectives, mission and vision. This alignment with priorities will reduce the risk of potential wastage of effort and resources. By ensuring that AI is working towards long-term objectives,

organisational consistency is improved and value-added initiatives and projects are prioritised. Furthermore, stakeholder buy-in will be facilitated if AI is perceived as a growth lever and a strategic tool rather than a technological trend. By defining a clear vision of the company's future with AI, technological advances are guided. The use of AI in project management must first and foremost aim to improve performance in order to create value for the company by offering tangible value for all stakeholders, right up to shareholders.

The main consequences are improved decision-making for managers, which can be adjusted in real time according to the insights provided by AI, and the savings made through better management of resources, which will boost the company's competitiveness in the marketplace.

- B. **Demonstrate the commitment of decision-makers:** Directors, members of the Executive and Management Committees and middle managers must show strong support for the use of AI to inspire confidence and enthusiasm within their teams. At present, one of the main difficulties is the lack of knowledge among senior managers about AI, which is often limited to generalities or hypothetical uses. For AI to be successfully integrated into project management, its use needs to be publicly supported, and the strategic advantages for the organisation need to be communicated, as well as the shortfalls for projects that do not use it. It is important to show a real willingness to allocate the financial resources and time needed to initiate its use in pilot projects.

The main consequences are the acceleration of adoption by employees, leading to a rapid reaping of the benefits of AI, and a strengthening of the image of the company as technologically advanced in its market and in attracting new talent.

- C. **Gradual adoption of AI:** artificial intelligence must be integrated gradually into project management processes. Sudden integration, covering all areas of project management, would run the risk of creating a lot of resistance to change through fear, anger or even aversion if the technology is not understood. It is a good idea to start with simple, low-risk strategic use cases before considering scaling up. The challenge is to deploy basic AI functionalities to familiarise teams with the technology without disrupting existing workflows.

An initial phase could include automated management of progress reports, workload prediction, planning optimisation, the use of virtual agents to assist teams, and analysis of stakeholder sentiment via internal communications. The next phase could incorporate more complex use cases requiring large amounts of historical data and in-depth analysis. For example, advanced human resources management, with the detection of in-house skills, predictive risk management, automated feedback and prediction of project success. It may also be appropriate to initiate the transformation on less complex projects or projects with less added value, because adopting AI requires training and familiarisation time, which can have major consequences depending on the project.

The main consequences are smoother change management to reduce operational disruption and the creation or reinforcement of a culture of innovation.

- D. **Integration of AI tools with existing systems needed for projects:** beyond integration with the company's PMIS (Project Management Information System), if one exists, AI solutions need to interface with a wider range of internal software to maximise the benefits of AI and avoid data redundancy. For example, an interconnection with HRIS (Human Resources Information System) tools can facilitate the implementation of functionalities for

detecting internal skills and profiles tailored to project needs. Interfacing with the FIMS (Financial Information Management System) is essential for deploying predictive budget management and automated expense tracking functions. Similarly, interfacing with communication and collaboration tools will improve the automated management of information sharing on project progress.

The main consequences are better access to accurate data, enabling better decision-making and better coordination and collaboration between the company's various departments, which will help ensure the success of projects.

- E. **Establish a framework for the use of artificial intelligence within the company, with clear boundaries:** in the medium term, most software will have integrated AI functions, some with similar capabilities. Project managers need to be supported in their choice of AI tool, depending on the specific needs of the project. This will optimise efficiency and maximise the use of resources by choosing the most appropriate tool, while promoting consistency of practice between project managers. For example, an AI tool may be effective in optimising the allocation of resources and project schedules, while another specialising in predictive analysis may excel in forecasting risks and identifying potential bottlenecks in the workflow.

The main consequences are a reduction in ambiguity leading to optimal use of resources and an increase in stakeholder confidence.

- F. **Define the roles and responsibilities between humans and AI in project management:** it is inevitable to clearly define which project management processes and tasks are delegated to artificial intelligence within the company. Every project management professional must easily identify what AI is allowed to do autonomously, what it must do in collaboration with humans, what it must not do without human supervision, and what humans must continue to do alone. For example, in creative or marketing processes, AI can speed up project implementation, but it will not innovate because it does not have the capacity to do so. And if it continues to be used, we need to determine what we are prepared to pay in the event of copyright problems, counterfeiting, plagiarism, theft of intellectual property, trademark or patent infringement.

The main consequences are reduced duplication of tasks, simplified collaboration between human teams and artificial intelligence tools, and increased quality for certain processes and deliverables.

- G. **Ongoing training and ethical behaviour:** learning how to use AI in project management is fundamental to getting to grips with it effectively and to guaranteeing safety and ethics. Resistance to change is reduced when teams receive training on the technologies deployed, and for AI training should cover usage, cybersecurity and ethics. It is important to have teams that are up to date with current advances in the field of AI and specifically with developments in project management. At the same time, it's a good idea to ensure that each member of staff has a weekly slot for ongoing independent training. This continuous updating will help the company to remain competitive in a rapidly changing environment. In addition, an evolution of training plans for project management professionals focused on strategy and the generation of benefits and value is vital if they are to develop the business acumen needed to focus on delivering benefits.

The main consequences are to have employees who are confident in their use of AI and motivated to improve practices as technology advances, as well as strengthening their vigilance to contribute to more secure and ethical projects.

- H. **Assessing skills and adapting jobs to the benefits of AI:** project service managers have an interest in developing the system for assessing the skills of project management professionals. Traditionally, a majority of companies based their assessments on criteria such as project success, compliance with costs, quality (as perceived by clients or sponsors), deadlines and return on investment. It is necessary either to construct new evaluation criteria or to add additional criteria, more focused on strategic and interpersonal skills and the value perceived by stakeholders. In addition, at the level of Human Resources departments, it is important to review and adapt the job descriptions and missions of professionals to better align their roles with the new requirements and opportunities created by AI, and to optimise new recruitment.

The main consequences are a strengthening of their role as leaders and strategists in the company and new opportunities for professional development.

- I. **Study of the impact of AI on project management processes:** a detailed inventory of the current situation of internal project management processes and tools is to be compared with a perspective of the expected state after the adoption of AI. High-performance tools and continuous monitoring of the progress of AI will help get closer to a beneficial return. Performance indicators to assess the results of AI and recurring alignment ensure that the end result is as close to reality as possible, depending on the data supplied to the AI. The effectiveness of AI requires constant review and analysis of performance data in order to target areas for improvement. The ongoing development of AI management through a variety of means is a future benefit for the company, which will remain de facto competitive.

The main consequences are having the insight to justify the investment in AI for project management, identifying the most relevant use cases, and implementing continuous improvement to adjust processes according to actual performance.

- J. **Maintain realistic expectations regarding the implementation of AI in project management:** AI cannot solve everything or revolutionise everything in project management. It is important to be realistic about the proposals produced by AI and the impact they will have on project management. A critical mind is essential to avoid unattainable objectives or other false directions. For example, taking into account the results of AI without first having entered all the sufficient or essential data is doomed to failure. The limits of AI should not be overlooked, as data, context and many other factors are bound to produce different results, even though it is a powerful technology. It is important to remember that AI produces work based on the data that a human being has given it. The results provided by AI will come from the quality of the data and the combination of AI with existing processes.

The main consequences are a reduction in the risk of frustration and disengagement and an increase in credibility and confidence in the use of project management.

- K. **Working with trade unions and employee representatives to successfully integrate AI into project management:** for any digital transformation, including these stakeholders from the outset, at least for information purposes, ensures that the introduction is aligned with

employees' needs and concerns, guaranteeing a smooth transition and reducing resistance. Trade unions and employee representatives defend workers' rights, and it is important to capitalise on their ability to identify the potential impact of AI on jobs, working conditions and the skills required. A climate of trust and transparency enables the successful adoption of new technologies, particularly when they are associated with a fairly widespread fear of jobs being replaced by AI.

The main consequences are proactive management of change management, leading to a reduction in resistance to change, better consideration of employees' needs and potential information relays to promote transparency.

7.2.5 Outlook

Several avenues of future research can be envisaged to deepen our understanding of the impact of AI on project management. Firstly, a quantitative study to measure the real and tangible time saved on project management tasks automated by AI would be relevant. It would be necessary to compare and quantify the time saved on similar projects managed with and without the use of AI tools.

It would also be interesting to carry out research into the quality gains perceived by stakeholders, such as clients, team members and sponsors, with and without the use of AI, by comparing concrete, measurable figures. This research would quantify the improvement in stakeholder satisfaction and quality of deliverables as a result of AI, providing tangible data to evaluate the effectiveness of AI tools.

In addition, an in-depth study of the changing role of the PMO in relation to the growth of AI implementation in project management would be essential. AI is changing the day-to-day tasks and responsibilities required of PMOs by enabling better monitoring of project progress, alerts on potential problems and automated management of project reports for both information gathering and sharing.

8 CONCLUSION

Our study shows that artificial intelligence improves project efficiency by automating repetitive tasks, optimising planning and enabling high-quality forecasts and predictions. The real “game changer” is to enable the project manager to be reallocated to complex value-added activities such as strategy, business value, profit generation, decision-making and interpersonal relations with stakeholders.

The rapid evolution of AI in the private sphere is influencing people's professional expectations and practices. A future systemic transformation of the world of work is a hypothesis. AI is transforming project management processes and roles by emphasising the human dimension rather than the technical. However, this effectiveness depends on the quality of the data, the project manager's skills in using artificial intelligence and interpreting the data, and the corporate culture.

Ethical challenges and concerns about project management skills have emerged. There is a need for a robust governance framework for the use of AI in project management, ensuring ethical use and appropriate training.

AI is seen as a tool to support the cognitive expansion of the Project Manager, as an augmented human. Despite fears and reticence, the perception of its positioning is that of a Personal Assistant to the Project Manager and not a competitor or potential replacement. In this sense, AI requires human supervision to guarantee results appropriate to the context, to limit dependency on its use by retaining its critical thinking and also to challenge its AI algorithms and reduce the risks of drift.

The adoption of AI in project management must be strategically aligned with organisational objectives, mission, vision and business goals. The challenge for senior managers is to support this technological transition by ensuring that AI is used to reinforce and not replace human capabilities. AI offers great potential for improving the performance of projects, but it cannot compensate for errors in the strategic alignment of projects, and requires a rigorous ethical framework. A change in the criteria used to assess the success of projects must place the emphasis on qualitative criteria such as strategic alignment and the impact on stakeholders, over and above the traditional metrics of cost, quality and time.

In conclusion, AI has major potential to improve project management performance, but requires human supervision, adequate training of professionals and strategic alignment to guarantee its effectiveness and ethics.

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